
**EXPERIENCES OF TEACHERS IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS
USING MOTHER TONGUE-BASED MULTILINGUAL
INSTRUCTION ACROSS SOUTH LUZON**

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to determine teachers' experiences in teaching Mathematics using Mother Tongue-Based instruction. The Philippine curriculum for Kindergarten to Grade 3 emphasizes using the mother tongue in teaching and learning Mathematics. The study used qualitative research design to gain data on the experiences, challenges, and strategies of teachers in South Luzon. The study revealed that Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education significantly improves instructional practices and student learning outcomes in Mathematics. MTB-MLE enhances engagement, comprehension, and problem-solving, fostering confidence and active class participation. However, despite its benefits, MTB-MLE presents challenges for teachers, including language barriers and resource limitations. Translation difficulties and inadequate instructional materials hinder student comprehension and engagement in Mathematics learning. Moreover, the results suggest that teachers' training programs focusing on MTB-MLE implementation strategies should be conducted and provide ongoing support and resources for educators. There should be enough support to teachers in implementing MTB-MLE effectively by providing leadership, resources, and professional development opportunities.

Keywords: *MTB-MLE, Mathematics, Experiences of Teachers, Positive Experiences, Negative Experiences, Challenges of Teacher, Parental Involvement,*

INTRODUCTION

Learning in one's mother tongue (MT), commonly referred to as the native language, is gaining increasing popularity both locally and globally, with organizations such as UNESCO and UNICEF endorsing this approach (Burton, 2013; Jacob, 2016). Governments in countries like Bangladesh, India, Nepal, and Papua New Guinea have shown growing interest in incorporating mother tongue instruction to advance MT education. Since the inception of the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) initiative in 2009, there have been expanded scholarship opportunities in the Philippines for learning in one's mother tongue. typically, during their critical developmental period, or it can be the first language learned, the one they are most proficient in, use the most frequently, and strongly identify with (Kosonen & Young, 2009).), advocating for bilingual and multilingual education across all schooling levels and promoting learners' right to receive education in their language to foster inclusivity and preserve linguistic diversity.

Language plays an important role in understanding Mathematical concepts. Familiarity or lack of it may determine the failures and success. Human beings since in the history used language to communicate, resolve conflicts, and solve numerical problems. It is one attribute that sets humans apart from all other creatures and binds humans together across all geographic barriers. Language serves as the bridge to understanding. Thus, even learning Mathematics requires linguistic skills. In recent years, there has been a growing recognition of the importance of embracing learners' mother tongues as a foundation for learning. The Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) policy has been at the forefront of educational reform efforts in the Philippines, emphasizing the use of native languages as a medium of instruction in the early years of schooling. This approach aims to improve comprehension, enhance critical thinking, and foster a deeper understanding of subjects, including Mathematics.

In the Philippines, one of the latest developments in the educational system is the Mother Tongue – Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE). MTB-MLE refers to the use of learners' mother tongue and two or more additional languages as Languages of Instruction (LoI) in school. In other contexts, the term is used to describe bilingual education across multiple language communities—each community using its mother tongue aside from the official school language of instruction. In South Asia multilingual education usually follows the first definition, learning and using multiple languages in school.

As South Luzon's educational landscape adapts to the MTB-MLE framework, it is crucial to understand the experiences of teachers on the frontlines of this transformative shift. This research is the rich tapestry of educators' experiences in teaching Mathematics using mother tongue-based multilingual education in South Luzon.

This introductory exploration, will outline the context and significance of this study, highlight the objectives, and provide a glimpse into the methods employed to capture the perspectives of these dedicated educators. Through the voices of South Luzon's teachers, it aims to unravel the challenges, successes, and lessons learned in implementing MTB-MLE in Mathematics instruction, shedding light on the path toward a more inclusive and effective education system.

In addition to adding to the expanding corpus of knowledge on multilingual education, this study provides insightful information that can guide curriculum design, policy decisions, and pedagogical approaches in South Luzon and elsewhere. Gaining insight into the experiences of educators can help create a mathematics education system that is more egalitarian and culturally sensitive, eventually promoting the holistic development of the students in the area.

Research Questions

1. What are the positive and negative experiences of teachers in teaching Mathematics in primary using Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Instruction?
 - 1.1 Tagalog
 - 1.2 Bicol
 2. What are the challenges towards the use of MTB-MLE as a medium of instruction in Mathematics encountered by the teachers?
 - 2.1 Tagalog
 - 2.2 Bicol
 3. What coping mechanism of teachers in addressing challenges encountered by the Teachers in Teaching Mathematics using Mother Tongue –Multilingual Instruction?
 - 3.1 Tagalog
 - 3.2 Bicol
 4. What program can be made to enhance the sustainability and effectiveness of using Mother Tongue in Teaching Mathematics?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research used a qualitative research design to gain in-depth insights into the experiences, challenges, and strategies of teachers in South Luzon. Qualitative research is well-suited for exploring complex phenomena and understanding the lived experiences of participants. This design allows for a nuanced exploration of the multifaceted aspects of MTB-MLE in Mathematics instruction.

Research Locale

Luzon sits at the northern end of the Philippines and is the country's largest and most populous island. It's known for its mountains. Southern Luzon is the Bicol region, which encompasses the remainder of Southern Luzon and includes the mainland provinces of Camarines Norte, Camarines Sur, Albay, and Sorsogon, and the islands of Catanduanes and Masbate. Quezon is officially the Province in the Philippines located in the Calabarzon region of Luzon. Kalilayan was the first known name of the province upon its creation in 1591. The study is to be conducted across selected elementary schools in Quezon and Bicol Region. The researcher chose the school in Quezon respondents namely, Pedro Cabangon Elementary School Located at Brgy. Mascariña, Quezon, Quezon and Del Pilar Elementary School Located at Brgy. Del Pilar Quezon, Quezon. While across the Bicol Region, Dygico Elementary School Sta Elena Camarines Norte and San Pedro Elementary School San Pedro, Camarines Norte. The participants were composed of 6 teachers in Quezon District who are actively teaching MTB-MLE and teachers from Grades 1-3 in Dygico Elementary School and San Pedro Elementary School.

The choice of South Luzon is based on its linguistic diversity and the significant implementation of MTB-MLE in the region.

Table 1. Respondents of the study

District/Division	School	Mother Tongue	Number of Respondents
District of Quezon, Division of Quezon	Pedro Cabangon Elementary School	Tagalog	3
	Del Pilar Elementary School	Tagalog	3
Sta. Elena District Division of Camarines Norte	Dygico Elementary School	Bicol	3
San Pedro District Division of Camarines Norte	San Pedro Elementary School	Bicol	3
Total			12

RESULTS

Part 1. The Positive and Negative Experiences of Teachers in Teaching Mathematics in Primary Using Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Instruction

Table 2

The Positive Experiences of Teachers in Teaching Mathematics in Primary Using Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Instruction in Tagalog

Theme	Sub-theme	Experiences
Positive Experiences	Learners Engagement	<p>Ang paggamit ng Mother tongue sa pagtuturo ng math ay may positibong resulta dahil mas naiintihan nila ang aralin nasasagot nila ng mas Madali ang mga suliranin o problem solving dahil mas Madali nilang maunawaan ang mga katanungan.</p> <p>Malaki ang naitutulong MTB In teaching -learning Mathematics, dahil nakakaresponse agad sila sa mga tanong ng guro.</p> <p>My learners understand the lesson clearly they are not ashamed in participating the activities dahil nga sa sila ay nakakapagsalita ng ating native dialect na mother tongue which is tagalog.</p> <p>Based on experiences learners easily understand the activities gamit ang mother tongue</p>

		<p>Mas madali intindihin mula isa hanggang sampu ok naman ang paggamit ng MTB Ok naman kasi nga yong panuto tagalog.</p> <p>Sa Mathematics kapag mother tongue mas nauunawaan nila.</p>
	Conceptual Clarity	<p>Sa mathematical concept kagaya ng sinabi ko kapag may mga problem solving mas Madali na nilang maunawan ito ex four fundamentals pagdadagdag mas Madali nila itong maunawaan</p> <p>Sa problem solving mas Madali lng nilang ma analyze ang mga situation kapag Mother tongue ang gamit.</p> <p>Dahil nga sa mother tongue ang gamit nila mas malinaw na sa kanila mga instruction mas Madali na nilang nasasagutan ang mga lesson at exam sa Mathematics.</p> <p>With the used of MTB as a medium instruction mas nauunawan nila ang lesson pagpapaliwanag ng mga procedure mas Madali nilang maintindihan. Learners answer and cooperate easily in most activities when they easily understand the task given to them.</p> <p>Sa akin po pinapababaw ko pa po ung mga salita para mas maunawaan</p>
	Teaching Effectiveness	<p>Napansin ko na mas mataas ang result ng mps nila unlike dati na mababa</p> <p>Lahat ng mga learners ay nagpaparticipate sa mga activies at nasasagot nila ng tama ang mga problem kaya alam ko na mas effective ang aking pagtuturo sa kanila.</p> <p>Sometimes some mathematical terminology are hindi madaling mtranslate sa tagalog pero dahil nga sa mother tongue mas nagging effective naman ung teaching ko.</p>

		<p>Mas madali sa min bilang guro magprepare ng materials mas Madali mag isip ng concept kasi ng MTB.</p> <p>For me as a teacher, I easily find the effectiveness of my teaching strategies and how I use them to help learners continue to the next lesson.</p> <p>Active po silang sumagot kapag mother tongue ang gamit dahil mas nauunawaan nila ang lesson</p>
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Table 2 presents the positive experiences of teachers utilizing Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) in teaching Mathematics in primary education, particularly in Tagalog, three main themes emerge from the data: Learners Engagement, Conceptual Clarity, and Teaching Effectiveness, each highlighting specific advantages observed by the teachers.

In terms of learners' Engagement, teachers report that learners understand lessons better and can answer questions more readily when taught in their mother tongue. This improved comprehension leads to more active participation and immediate responses to teacher inquiries. Furthermore, using Tagalog reduces learners' fear or shame, encouraging them to participate more willingly in classroom activities. The cultural relevance of commands and instructions in Tagalog resonates more deeply with learners, fostering a sense of connection and comfort in the learning environment.

When it comes to Conceptual Clarity, the use of the mother tongue simplifies problem-solving for learners. Mathematical concepts and problems explained in Tagalog are easier for learners to grasp and analyze. Teachers also find that instructions given in the mother tongue are clearer, helping learners to understand and complete their lessons and exams more effectively. This clarity leads to improved cooperation among learners as they can better comprehend and follow the tasks assigned to them.

Regarding Teaching Effectiveness, teachers observe that learners' mean percentage scores have improved, indicating better academic performance. The use of Tagalog encourages all learners to participate in activities and solve problems correctly, demonstrating the effectiveness of this teaching approach. Additionally, teachers find it easier to prepare materials and conceptualize teaching strategies when using Tagalog, which enhances their overall teaching effectiveness. Despite some challenges in translating technical mathematical terms, the overall benefits of using the mother tongue outweigh these difficulties, resulting in more effective teaching.

It implies that the positive experiences of teachers in using Tagalog as MTB-MLE in teaching Mathematics underscore its potential to enhance learning outcomes and promote learners' engagement. By addressing challenges and leveraging the benefits of MTB-MLE, educators can create a more effective and inclusive learning environment that caters to the diverse linguistic needs of learners in primary education.

Table 3

The Negative Experiences of Teachers in Teaching Mathematics in Primary Using Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Instruction in Tagalog

Theme	Sub-theme	Experiences
<i>Negative Experiences</i>	<i>Language Barriers</i>	<p><i>May naexperience na ako about jan yong bata ay galing sa ibang lugar medyo nahirapan ang bata dahil used na used siya sa mother tongue niya medyo mahirap sa part naming dagdag trabaho dahil kailangan mo talaga gumawa paraan para makaunawa ung bata.</i></p> <p><i>In teaching Mathematics may mga termenologies sa MTB na mahirap maunawaan ng learners like grade one, mas Madali sa kanila ung greater than kaysa sa labis ng isa. Sa fraction naman yong $\frac{1}{4}$ ay mas madalas nilang maunawaan kaysa sangkapat, at sa counting or reading.</i></p> <p><i>Yong ibang tagalog words ay nahihirapan silang unawain</i></p> <p><i>May Mga case ako dati na yong bata ay from other regions like bicol na kung saan yon ung nakasanayan nila kaya kailangan ko pang mag search ng translation ng dialect nila.</i></p> <p><i>For me, some terminologies used in Mathematics were complicated to translate in the mother tongue and they are also complicated to understand.</i></p>
	<i>Learners Reception</i>	<p><i>Kagaya ng sinabi ko ung bata ay galing sa ibang lugar yong bata ay nagkaroon ng struggle.</i></p> <p><i>When teaching Mathematics in Elementary grade there are some challenges encountered one of them is mas mahirap silang maunawaan ang ibang mga salita na isinalin sa tagalog</i></p> <p><i>Nahihirapan lalo na pag yong mga words ay bago sa pandinig nila.</i></p>

		<p><i>Mahirap po kasi meron used sa english nahihirapan talaga sila.</i></p> <p><i>Yes! there were instances when learners were confused and did not understand it easily</i></p> <p><i>Challenging talaga siya sa part ko lalo na at nasanay sila sa English kaya need humanap ng paraan na mas mapadali nila mainitindihan yong mga instruction.</i></p>
	<p><i>Resource Limitations</i></p>	<p><i>Kulang tayo sa mga materials kaya sana maglabas pa sila ng maraming books na nakasalin sa Mother Tongue.</i></p> <p><i>Kulang at pilit kang gagawa ng mga instructional materials par mas maunawaan ng mga learners ang lesson na nakaka consume pa ng maraming oras para lng maunawaan nila.</i></p> <p><i>Minsan nakakaapekto ito sa mga mag-aaral lalo na at di sapat ang resources</i></p> <p><i>Medyo po kasi kulang yong mga materials books but nagagawan ng paraan.</i></p> <p><i>Teachers had a hard time executing the lesson because of limited resources and also the lack of training and takes time for me and I think other teachers to go to the next lesson</i></p> <p><i>The teacher had a hard time to execute the lesson because of limited resources and the lack of training and takes time for me and I think to another teacher to go to the next lesson</i></p>

Table 3 presents the negative experiences of teachers in teaching Mathematics in primary using Tagalog as a mother tongue-based multilingual education.

Teachers face significant challenges in teaching Mathematics using Mother Tongue Multilingual Education (MTB), particularly due to language barriers. learners, especially those from different linguistic backgrounds, struggle to grasp mathematical

concepts presented in Tagalog, even though they are more accustomed to their mother tongue. This leads to difficulties in communication and comprehension, hindering effective teaching and learning. To address language barriers, educators need to adopt diverse instructional strategies that cater to the linguistic diversity of learners. This may include providing bilingual or multilingual resources, offering language support programs, and fostering a culturally responsive learning environment. Additionally, teacher training programs should focus on equipping educators with the necessary skills and tools to effectively teach Mathematics in multilingual settings, thereby improving learner engagement.

The reception of Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Education (MTB) in Mathematics varies among learners, influenced by factors such as language background and instructional support. Some learners may struggle to understand mathematical concepts presented in Tagalog, leading to confusion and frustration. However, with adequate support and encouragement, learners demonstrate resilience and willingness to learn, highlighting the importance of fostering a supportive learning environment. Educators must prioritize creating inclusive learning environments where learners feel supported and valued, regardless of their language background. This involves providing individualized support to learners who may struggle with language comprehension, implementing collaborative learning activities that promote peer interaction and support, and celebrating linguistic and cultural diversity in the classroom. By addressing learners' diverse needs and fostering a positive learning environment, educators can enhance learners' reception of MTB in Mathematics and promote equitable access to education for all learners.

Resource limitations pose significant challenges to the implementation of Mother tongue-based Multilingual Education (MTB) in Mathematics, impacting the quality of instruction and learning outcomes. Teachers often lack sufficient instructional materials and training opportunities, forcing them to create local materials and adapt teaching strategies to address resource gaps. This not only consumes valuable time and effort but also affects the effectiveness of teaching and learning. Addressing resource limitations requires a multi-faceted approach that involves both policy-level interventions and localized strategies. Governments and educational authorities should prioritize investment in education infrastructure, including the provision of adequate instructional materials, training opportunities for teachers, and support for curriculum development in local languages. Additionally, educators can leverage existing resources more efficiently through collaborative networks, sharing best practices, and tapping into community resources. By addressing resource limitations comprehensively, educators can enhance the implementation of MTB in Mathematics and improve Learners' learning outcomes.

Furthermore, a balance between mastery of the facts of higher-order thinking skills translated into the native dialect must be forged by the teachers in their choice of a teaching strategy, selecting an appropriate teaching strategy suited for the level of the learner, and mastery of the prerequisite knowledge or concept as translated in the native dialect (Ball, 2010) as cited by Tortola (2021)

Table 4

The Positive Experiences of Teachers in Teaching Mathematics in Primary Using Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Instruction in Bicol

Theme	Sub-theme	Experiences
Positive Experiences	Learners Engagement	<p>Actually, ang case naming ay tagalog speaking nagkaton lamang ay karamihan ng mga estudyante ay Bicolano. Base sa experience namin sa mtb-mle, mas productive nilang gamitin sapagkat nauunawaan nila dahil nita-translate namin ito sa tagalog o sa bicol para mas maintindihan nila pero siyempre may mga mathematical term na hindi naman talaga maitra-translate.</p> <p>Mas Maganda mas naiintindihan nila lalo na sa mga problem situation unlike before na English ang gamit mas Maganda naiintidihan nila ung mga problem</p> <p>Pag kase mtb-mle, nung mag training ng k-12 mas maiintindihan nila sa tagalog pero yung mga terminology ay nagiiba na, nagiging mahirap. Kaya ang ginawa ko Nagtagalog ako ng sampuan, isahan, nagreklamo ang mga bata</p> <p>May enhacement yong kanilang learning ung mga bata ay nag increase ang confidence dahil mas naiintindihan nila yong lesson.</p> <p>Based po sa aking experience learners will easily understand using MTB-MLE as a medium of instruction</p> <p>Mas ok yong sa ngayon kasi nga mother tongue so mas naipapaliwanag ng maayos</p>
	Conceptual Clarity	<p>Malinaw na sa kanila ang lenggwahe kaya nagiging mas madali para sa estudyante na maintindihan ang mga konsepto o terms ng matematika.</p> <p>Naeexpress din nila mas naiintidihan nila mas mganda yong interaction naiintidihan nila lalo na sa mga problem solving.</p> <p>Pag mother tongue mas Madali nilang maunawaan pag sinabi mong magdadagdag nasasagot agad nila ung tanong</p>

		<p><i>Using mother tongue in mathematical concept mas malinaw na sa kanila yong mga instruction dahil naiintihan na nga nila ito.</i></p> <p><i>Tama yon mam lalo na sa problem solving naiintidihan na agad nila yong panuto kasi mother tongue ang gamit dati kailangan mo pang itranslate para maunawaan.</i></p> <p><i>Learners answer and cooperate Easily when an easy task is given to them</i></p>
	<p><i>Teaching Effectiveness</i></p>	<p><i>In teaching effectiveness, mas Madali nilang nauunawaan dahil araw-araw na naituturo, ang problema lang na kapag sa higher grade ay English so nagkakaran sila ng after shocked sila pero epektibo talaga siya.</i></p> <p><i>Di ba sabi ko kanina mayron kaming batang ang gamit sa bahay ay dos bente pero sinasabi ko sa kaniya na iyon ay Spanish word tapos tinranslate ko na lng na yong dos ay dalawa mas Maganda ang tagalog kaya lng mas sanay sila sa ingles dahil ang tinuturo sa bahay ay one two three</i></p> <p><i>Gumagamit ng mga mateials para mas maging effective yong pagtuturo ko</i></p> <p><i>Ang teacher ay dapat na maging effective sa pagtuturo para mas lumawak ang understanding at pagkatuto ng bata.</i></p> <p><i>Effective po lalo na sa exam mabilis nilang maunawaan mabilis nilang masasagutan yong mga exam.</i></p> <p><i>Effective po kase mother tongue.</i></p>

Table 4 presents the positive experiences of teachers employing Bicol as their Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) in teaching Mathematics in the Bicol region focusing on learners’ engagement, conceptual clarity, and teaching effectiveness.

Teachers observe that using MTB-MLE significantly enhances engagement, especially when lessons are translated into Tagalog or Bicol. Most learners are Bicolano,

and they respond better to instruction in their native language, leading to more productive lessons. This approach helps learners comprehend better and participate more actively. Teachers note that learners understand problem situations better in their mother tongue compared to English, which was previously used. Although there are challenges with terminology differences, especially when transitioning between Tagalog and Bicol, the overall engagement and confidence of learners have increased. This boost in confidence is attributed to their improved understanding of the lessons, facilitated by the use of their mother tongue.

Using the mother tongue in teaching mathematical concepts enhances learners' understanding and clarity. Teachers find that instructions are clearer, and learners grasp mathematical terms and concepts more effectively. When learners speak and learn in their mother tongue, they can express themselves better and engage more meaningfully in problem-solving activities. This clarity extends to specific instructions, making it easier for learners to follow along and respond accurately. Teachers report that 'earners immediately understand and apply instructions when taught in their mother tongue, reducing the need for repeated explanations. This immediate comprehension leads to smoother classroom interactions and better academic performance in Mathematics.

Teachers experience improved teaching effectiveness with the use of Bicol as MTB-MLE. Daily instruction in the mother tongue helps learners understand lessons more easily, leading to better academic outcomes. Although there is a noted challenge when learners transition to higher grades where English is the primary medium of instruction, the foundational understanding built through MTB-MLE remains beneficial. Teachers find that using materials in the mother tongue makes lessons more effective and helps learners quickly grasp and retain mathematical concepts. This effectiveness is particularly evident in exams, where learners demonstrate quicker understanding and accurate responses. Teachers emphasize that being effective in their instruction is crucial for expanding learners learning and understanding. Overall, the use of the mother tongue proves to be an effective strategy in enhancing the teaching and learning process in primary Mathematics education.

The positive experiences with MTB-MLE in Bicol highlight the need for educational policies that support multilingual education, especially in regions with diverse linguistic backgrounds. Developing comprehensive bilingual or multilingual resources can help standardize terminology and improve understanding. Providing continuous professional development and training for teachers in MTB-MLE methodologies is essential to equip them with effective strategies for engaging learners and enhancing conceptual clarity. Allocating adequate resources, including textbooks and teaching aids in both Tagalog and regional dialects, is crucial to support MTB-MLE. Additionally, involving parents and the community in the educational process can reinforce classroom learning and provide additional support for learners. Regular assessment and feedback mechanisms can help identify best practices and areas for improvement, ensuring the sustained success of MTB-MLE programs. By addressing these implications, the effectiveness of teaching Mathematics in primary education using MTB-MLE in Bicol can be further enhanced, leading to better academic outcomes and Learners' engagement.

According to Englis, & Boholano (2021), the use of mother-tongue in teaching Mathematics is effective in acquiring Mathematical knowledge. The teachers are well-prepared in terms of content and instructional material preparation. Moreover, the contextualized and innovative model in teaching Mathematics using mother-tongue helps in acquiring basic skills in Mathematics hence, to help Mathematics teachers making use of this model, this finding would be a great help to the primary teachers in Mathematics as well as the institution the value of contextualization and innovation as core functions in teaching strategies where the school administrators will continually support the teachers development plan and provide the tools and equipment needed on teaching.

Table 5
The Negative Experiences of Teachers in Teaching Mathematics in Primary Using Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Instruction in Bicol

Theme	Sub-theme	Bicol
Negative Experiences	Language Barriers	<p><i>Sabi nga diba every individual is a unique. Sa case ko ngayon, hati-hati ay, may mga hirap sa tagalog so kailangan ko itranslate sa bicol pero nahihirapan pa rin sila ,pero may ibang estudyante na mas naiintindihan sa English. So kapag hindi nila nauunawan sa mtb-mle ay ginagamitan na ng English. May ibang estudyante na magtatanong talaga ng “ma’am ano po yung hatiin sa ganun” ay diba divide yun kaya kailangan pa itranslate. Pero kase may mga malalalim na salita na hindi naman matratranslate sa mtb-mle.</i></p> <p><i>Minsan cguro kulang din ang experience ng bata sa mga vocabulary, hindi nila masyadong maintindihan dahil may mas malalim na terms katulad sa problem solving (Ano ang itinatanong?tagalog na un di pa rin nila maintindihan)</i></p> <p><i>Hindi ako nagbibicol pero nakakaintindi ako ng Bicol dahil taga Lopez ako kaya ng magkaroon ako ng learner na taga bicol medyo nahirapan ako kaya nagresearch ako ng salita ng bicol para maunawaan niya ako siyempre kinakausap ko siya ng bicol dahil hindi niya maintindihan ang salita ng tagalog.</i></p> <p><i>Marami tayong naeencounter na mga words lalo na pagmay transfer galing sa ibang lugar bukod sa nahihirapan ang bata ganun din si</i></p>

		<p><i>teacher kasi pareho nilang hindi alam yong mother tongue nila.</i></p> <p><i>Katulad ko mam may Bicol akong eskwela ang sinasabi hala sige imikin mo at translate ko nag bibicol ako kapag may mga studyante akong bicol sa place value hirap sila sa mother tongue kase mas sanay sila sa English</i></p> <p><i>may mga bata kasi na sanay sa English lalo na sa numbers may mga case kami na nagsasabi na mam translate mo nga sa ng English.</i></p>
	<p><i>Learners Reception</i></p>	<p><i>Ay kadakol baga, o dakalunod o ibig-sabihin ay madami rin. Kase hindi naman lahat ng bata ay mas nauunawaan nila ang matematika base sa pag-aaral nila. Sabi nila pag mother tongue ay effective ni waray pero sa aming sitwasyon baga, effective kung lahat ng bata ay matutukan pero katulad dito na kapag nasa loob ng bahay ay babalik yung bata tapos sasabihin nila ay di raw naintindihan ng mga magulang nung bata at magtatanong ulit. Yan ang problema, mother tongue nga ay di makasagot su magura wara na, nganga baga.</i></p> <p><i>Ang mga bata hindi pare pareho ang ability may mga bata na magaling sa math meron namang slow so pag ginagamit natin ang mtb dahil pareho kami ng language naintindihan naman niya</i></p> <p><i>Mayron nag struggle na bata sabi ko nga lalo na kapag yong bata ay galing ng ibang lugar na iba ang mother tongue halimbawa galing bicol marunong ako magbicol kasi galing ako ng Cam Sur kaya Madali sa akin dahil kaya kung magbicol katulad ng saro, duwa,tulo, binibicol ko siya siyempre pero at the same time titranslate ko din in tagalog.</i></p> <p><i>Ay meron di ba English ang gamit nila sa day Care kaya pagdating sa Grade I may mga nahihirapan dahil sanay sila sa tagalog bukod</i></p>

		<p><i>don mahaba ang tagalog kapag isinulat kaya umaayaw sila magsulat.</i></p>
	<p><i>Resource Limitations</i></p>	<p><i>So, Resource limitations Diba ngayon ay digital na, ay gapos na lang ang resources kada method mi tanghali maka og-tug di an ki maray ng makautol ng makaupod baga, pulpugol tayo makaugod lalo na mang ganiyan tayo ay uginat IM na o numeracy. Kung ang tanong dun Ay English ay mother tounge, ay patay baga. So lahat ng resources, kailangan mo i-provide yun para maintidihan ma pa real objects, pudpud na ba yung deped diyan na mga indigenous materials. Walang limitasyon, kung hanggang kaya ipasok para maunawaan ay ipapasok.</i></p> <p><i>Kulang kami ng mga books lalo ma last year merong mga hindi nagsuli lalo nat may mga books kaming ang gamit na ay sampuan na words. Pero meron naman nakukuhaan lalo na ngayon.</i></p> <p><i>Yong mga books ng mag K-12 kaunti lng nabigay samin kaya nag share ang bata tapos sulat na lng sa board.</i></p> <p><i>Ang ating teaching materials ay limitado lng pero may mga internet access naman kaso dito samin medyo mahina.</i></p> <p>Kanya kanyang provide at may mga teachers guide naman</p>

Table 5 presents the negative experiences of teachers in teaching Mathematics in primary using Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Instruction in Bicol

The experience of language barriers in Mother Tongue Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) in Bicol underscores the complexity of linguistic diversity in educational settings. Teachers face challenges in translating mathematical concepts from Tagalog to Bicol, as some terms may not have direct equivalents. Additionally, learners may struggle with deeper concepts like problem-solving due to language limitations, impacting their comprehension and learning experiences. Despite efforts to bridge the language gap,

such as using English for clarification, challenges persist for both learners and teachers, particularly when learners come from different linguistic backgrounds.

The reception of MTB-MLE in Mathematics among learners in Bicol varies based on individual abilities, linguistic backgrounds, and previous experiences with Mathematics instruction. While MTB-MLE may be effective for some learners, others may struggle, particularly if they come from different linguistic backgrounds or have varying levels of mathematical proficiency. Teachers play a crucial role in supporting Learners understanding by providing language support and adapting instructional strategies to meet diverse learning needs. However, challenges persist, particularly when learners transition from daycare to Grade I, where they may encounter difficulties due to language preferences and writing conventions.

Resource limitations pose significant challenges to the effective implementation of MTB-MLE in Mathematics instruction in Bicol. Teachers lack adequate instructional materials, including books and digital resources, impacting their ability to deliver high-quality instruction. Despite efforts to supplement resources with internet access and teacher guides, limitations persist, leading to reliance on shared materials and improvised teaching methods. Additionally, challenges arise in accessing indigenous materials and ensuring equitable distribution of resources across schools.

It implies that language barriers require a multi-pronged approach that acknowledges the diverse linguistic landscape of the classroom. Educators should collaborate with local communities to develop comprehensive language resources that cater to the specific needs of learners, including translations of mathematical terms and concepts. Professional development programs should focus on equipping teachers with strategies for effectively teaching in multilingual environments, such as code-switching and incorporating culturally relevant examples. Moreover, educational policies should prioritize the inclusion of diverse languages in curriculum development and instructional materials, ensuring equitable access to education for all learners. Enhancing Learner's reception of MTB-MLE in Mathematics requires a holistic approach that addresses individual learning needs and linguistic diversity. Educators should implement differentiated instruction strategies that accommodate diverse learning styles and abilities, providing additional support for learners who may struggle with mathematical concepts. Furthermore, a collaboration between educators, parents, and communities is essential to create a supportive learning environment that values linguistic diversity and promotes academic success for all learners. By fostering a culture of inclusivity and support, educators can empower learners to overcome challenges and thrive in Mathematics education. Moreover, resource limitations required systemic changes at both policy and practice levels. Educational authorities should prioritize investment in educational infrastructure, including the provision of sufficient instructional materials and digital resources, to support effective teaching and learning. Furthermore, professional development programs should equip teachers with the skills and knowledge to utilize available resources effectively and adapt teaching strategies to meet diverse learning needs. Collaborative efforts between government agencies, educational institutions, and

community stakeholders are essential to ensure equitable access to resources and promote educational equity in Bicol and beyond.

Part II. The Challenges Towards the Use of MTB-MLE as a Medium of Instruction in Mathematics Encountered by the Teachers

Table 6

The Challenges Towards the Use of MTB-MLE as a Medium of Instruction in Mathematics Encountered by the Teachers in Tagalog

Theme	Sub-theme	Experiences
<i>Challenges of MTB-MLE in Mathematics</i>	<i>Curriculum Alignment</i>	<p><i>Di po ako sure kung align kasi nga English ang curriculum guide tapos tagalog mo siya ituturo</i></p> <p><i>Challenge yong paggamit dahil walang training lalo na yong mga bagong guro dahil ng una pa lng talagang ang gamit ay English</i></p> <p><i>It is appropriate in primary level lalo na ta karamihan sa mga bata ay di nakaka intindi ng Ingles but mas sanay sila na English ang tawag sa bilang.</i></p> <p><i>Di po masyado kasi English nga sa CG need mo pa translate yong iba. Dagdag trabaho kay teacher kung pano niya ituturo yong lesson</i></p> <p><i>Hindi siya align Hirap si teacher in executing lessons although tagalog mo sya ituturo may mga words talaga na kahit kami hirap maunawaan ito.</i></p> <p><i>For me, some terminologies in Mathematics were complicated to translate into their mother tongue and they are also complicated to understand by learners</i></p>
	<i>Teacher Preparedness</i>	<i>Para sa akin di siya ganun ka challenging dahil mas nakatulong siya sa akin basta gamit ay mother tongue</i>

		<p><i>Siguro yong mga cahallenges naming yong ibang bata ay di particular in counting numbers</i></p> <p><i>Siyempre pag tagalog mas Madali nilang matulungan ang mga anak nila</i></p> <p><i>I need more training to help me as a teacher to execute the lesson and to disseminate the effectiveness of using MTB-MLE</i></p>
	<i>Parental Involvement</i>	<p><i>Mas aware ang magulang dahil un ang gamit nila sa bahay pero minsan may mga trermenology na hindi nila maintindihan.</i></p> <p><i>Sa parents naman pag may mga homework yong mga learner na hindi rin maunawaan ng mga parents yong mga instruction na naka-MTB-MLE dahil ung mga siinaunang parents ay nasanay sila ang gamit ay ingles</i></p> <p><i>Yong di napapafollow up sa bahat ang mga bata</i></p> <p><i>Parents should have a positive attitude towards helping and should follow up on the learnings of the learners at home so that the skills that were learned at school will not be easily forgotten</i></p> <p><i>Sa parent wala masyado pakialam sa mga anak</i></p>

Table 5 presents the challenges to the use of MTB-MLE as a medium of instruction in Mathematics encountered by the teachers in Tagalog. Curriculum alignment highlights the challenges and successes of aligning the Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) approach with the Mathematics curriculum. Teachers express varying degrees of ease or difficulty in implementing MTB-MLE in Mathematics instruction, depending on their familiarity with the curriculum and the training they have received. While some teachers find it relatively easy to align the MTB-MLE approach with the curriculum, others struggle due to complex mathematical terminologies and lack of training. Despite these challenges, teachers acknowledge the benefits of using MTB-MLE, particularly in helping both teachers and learners understand lesson objectives and execute activities effectively. Enhancing curriculum alignment requires targeted support for teachers, including comprehensive training on curriculum objectives and strategies for

integrating MTB-MLE in Mathematics instruction. Professional development programs should focus on building teachers' capacity to effectively translate complex mathematical concepts into mother tongue languages and adapt instructional materials to suit diverse learning needs. Additionally, educational authorities should provide ongoing guidance and resources to support teachers in aligning MTB-MLE with the Mathematics curriculum, ensuring consistency and effectiveness in teaching practices.

Teacher preparedness underscores the challenges faced by teachers in implementing MTB-MLE in Mathematics due to inadequate training and preparation. Teachers express a need for more training to effectively execute lessons and disseminate the effectiveness of using MTB-MLE. Some teachers attribute challenges in teaching mother tongue languages to their lack of preparation and training, particularly in adapting instructional strategies to suit diverse learning needs. However, despite these challenges, teachers recognize the importance of continuous professional development in enhancing their capacity to deliver high-quality MTB-MLE instruction. Improving teacher preparedness requires comprehensive training programs that equip educators with the knowledge, skills, and resources needed to effectively implement MTB-MLE in Mathematics instruction. Educational authorities should prioritize professional development opportunities that address teachers' specific needs, including training on curriculum alignment, language proficiency, and instructional strategies. Additionally, mentorship programs and peer support networks can provide ongoing guidance and assistance to teachers as they navigate the challenges of implementing MTB-MLE in Mathematics. By investing in teacher preparedness, educational stakeholders can ensure that educators are equipped to deliver equitable and effective Mathematics instruction in multilingual settings. Parental involvement highlights the role of parents in supporting MTB-MLE in Mathematics education and the challenges they face in understanding and engaging with the curriculum. Parents' awareness and understanding of MTB-MLE vary, with some being more familiar with the language used at home and others struggling to comprehend the terminology used in the curriculum. While some parents actively support their children's learning by assisting with homework, others may lack the knowledge or inclination to engage with the MTB-MLE approach.

Promoting parental involvement in MTB-MLE requires targeted outreach and support initiatives that empower parents to actively engage in their children's education. Schools and educational authorities should provide resources and information in languages accessible to parents, including translations of curriculum materials and guidance on how to support MTB-MLE at home. Additionally, parent-teacher collaboration platforms and workshops can facilitate communication and collaboration between educators and parents, fostering a supportive learning environment for learners. By promoting parental involvement, educators can enhance the effectiveness of MTB-MLE in Mathematics education and promote positive learning outcomes for all learners.

Melencion (2017) as cited by Tortola (2021), stated that some teachers are asked to teach some other language or vernacular, multilingual dialects that are unfamiliar to them. This points to the difficulty of using the MTBMLE since there are different variations of the mother tongue even in one locality.

Table 7

The Challenges Towards the Use of MTB-MLE as a Medium of Instruction in Mathematics Encountered by the Teachers in Bicol

Theme	Sub-theme	Experiences
<p><i>Challenges of MTB-MLE in Mathematics</i></p>	<p><i>Curriculum Alignment</i></p>	<p><i>Dito nga kami sa mtb-mle naglulukso ay kase hindi naman naming lahat nauunawaan ay kahit din ng mga bata, sa matematika naman ay may mga terms talaga na hindi talaga matra-translate sa mother tongue, kaya english na gagamtiin niyan kumbaga kailangan mo lang i-open sa bata na di mo yan kaya maintranslate sa tagalog, para alam nila kung ano ba ang mga pwedeng itranslate sa tagalog. Sa alignment di naman marami pa need enhance.</i></p> <p><i>Ayan namang curriculum, bago yan niimplement pinag-aralan but in some aspect kulang sila sa preparation.</i></p> <p><i>Hindi po masyado kasi marami mga terms na kahit guro nahihirapan kasi nga kulang sa explanation si teacher ang nahihirapan magiisip pa siya kung pano ito translate</i> <i>Dati nga kasi English kailangan mo pa explain sa mother tongue nila so ngayon hindi na kasi nga ang gamit na ay mtb pero yong once tens hundreds naforce si teacher na ituro talaga ito</i></p> <p><i>English sa curriculum guide tapos ang ituturo ay tagalog translate na lng sa mtb nila siyempre align naman.</i></p> <p><i>May mga estudyanteng galing sa ibang lugar like Bicol kasi may mga bumabalik dito sa atin a naninirahan na don na ung bata yon na yong nakagisnan na experience ko na po yon ayon po nagresearch ako ng dialect nila.</i></p>

	<p><i>Teacher Preparedness</i></p>	<p><i>Hindi masyado kase nga kulang pa ako sa trainings</i></p> <p><i>Challenging talaga sa amin bilang guro lalo na at pagdaating ng grade 4 english na ang gamit nila sa Mathematics. Kahit pa sabihin na mother tongue ang hirap pa rin sa part namin lalo na kapag ang bata ay walang interest at mas gusto nila ay English lalo na pagdating sa bilang.</i></p> <p><i>Sa mga bagong guro walang training hirap pa sila Oo meron tayong mga trainings, pero pili lang ang naattend dito sa min.</i></p> <p><i>Kaya sana magbigay ng training pa sa mga guro para mas maimprove pa ang kakayahan nila sa paggamit ng mother tongue.</i></p>
	<p><i>Parental Involvement</i></p>	<p><i>Mahirap sa magulang kase limatado o depende rin kung nag-aabyad ang magulang sa kanilang mga anak na fo-follow up nila yun. May iba kase na sariling sikap ang estudyante, wala kang makukuhang suporta sa magulang lalo na kapag single mother na may trabaho o isang kahig isang tuka бага dun nagiging mahirap. Kaya dun na inaasa sa school lalo na kapag bakasyon pero kapag supportive ang parents makikita mo talaga na sobrang nageexcell ang bata sa klase kase nakaka follow up.</i></p> <p><i>Yan ang pinaka problema. Maganda yung mga bata na ang parents nila ay supportive or yung mga maalwan kase mas natutukan nila ang bata. At yung mga bata nasa strugglers or struggling learner, kase yung mga magulang ay nagtrabaho kaya hindi na natutukan ang anak nila. At yung educational background nung parents, pano kung hindi rin alam ng magulang ang mga lessons pag nagtatanong ang bata. Yung textbook din kase dati ay iba ang textbook kase English talaga.</i></p>

		<p><i>Parental attitudes minsan pag nagpapahomework ako halimbawa isulat ang numerong ito minsan mali ang pangalan ng bilang kinse , dos kase yon yong nakanayan ng parents.</i></p>
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Table 7 presents the challenges towards the use of MTB-MLE as a medium of instruction in Mathematics encountered by the teachers in Bicol.

Curriculum alignment highlights both the challenges and successes in aligning the Mother Tongue Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) approach with the Mathematics curriculum in Bicol. Teachers express difficulties in translating certain mathematical terms into the mother tongue, necessitating the use of English for explanation. However, they also emphasize the importance of alignment between the curriculum and teaching practices, acknowledging the efforts made to ensure coherence and effectiveness in instruction. Teachers demonstrate adaptability in addressing challenges, such as providing translations for difficult terms, and recognize the value of implementing MTB-MLE despite its complexities.

Ensuring effective curriculum alignment requires ongoing collaboration and communication between educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers. Educational authorities should provide comprehensive guidance and resources to support teachers in aligning MTB-MLE with the Mathematics curriculum, including translations of difficult terms and clear guidelines for implementation. Additionally, professional development programs should equip teachers with the skills and knowledge needed to effectively integrate MTB-MLE into Mathematics instruction, fostering a deeper understanding of curriculum objectives and instructional strategies. By promoting alignment between the curriculum and teaching practices, educators can enhance the effectiveness of MTB-MLE in Mathematics education and improve learning outcomes for learners.

Teacher preparedness reflects the challenges and efforts involved in ensuring that educators are adequately trained and equipped to implement MTB-MLE in Mathematics instruction. Teachers express varying levels of preparedness, with some feeling confident in their training and others acknowledging the ongoing nature of professional development. Despite challenges, such as the transition to online training during the pandemic, teachers demonstrate a commitment to continuous improvement and recognize the importance of training in enhancing their effectiveness as educators.

Enhancing teacher preparedness requires sustained investment in professional development opportunities that address the specific needs of educators in implementing MTB-MLE in Mathematics instruction. Educational authorities should provide ongoing

training and support that is aligned with curriculum objectives and instructional priorities. Additionally, mentorship programs and peer collaboration can facilitate knowledge sharing and skill development among educators, fostering a culture of continuous learning and improvement. By prioritizing teacher preparedness, educational stakeholders can enhance the quality of Mathematics education and promote positive learning outcomes for all learners.

Parental involvement underscores the challenges and importance of parental support in facilitating Learners learning in MTB-MLE Mathematics education. Teachers note the impact of parental attitudes and engagement on learners' success, highlighting the influence of factors such as parental availability, educational background, and willingness to support their children's learning. Challenges arise when parents lack the time, resources, or understanding to effectively support their children's education, leading to disparities in Learners' outcomes.

Promoting parental involvement requires targeted efforts to engage and support parents in their children's education, particularly in understanding and supporting MTB-MLE Mathematics instruction. Schools can provide resources and guidance to parents on how to support their children's learning at home, including translations of curriculum materials and strategies for reinforcing mathematical concepts. Additionally, schools can foster a culture of collaboration between educators and parents, encouraging open communication and mutual support. By addressing barriers to parental involvement and promoting a supportive home learning environment, educators can enhance learners' success in MTB-MLE Mathematics education.

Part III. The Coping Mechanism of Teachers in Addressing Challenges Encountered by the Teachers in Teaching Mathematics Using Mother-Tongued- Based Multilingual Instruction

Table 8

The Coping Mechanism of Teachers in Addressing Challenges Encountered by the Teachers in Teaching Mathematics Using Mother Tongue – Based Multilingual Instruction in Tagalog

Theme	Sub-theme	Experiences
<i>Coping Mechanisms for Addressing Challenges</i>	<i>Curriculum Alignment</i>	<p><i>Pinag - aaralang Mabuti ang lesson at gumagawa ng mga instructional materials na mas maiintindihan ng mga learners lalo ma yong mga salita o terms na kanilang ginagamit dahil minsan may mga salita pa rin sila na hindi maintindihan.</i></p> <p><i>Para mas Madali nilang matutunan Yong lesson mas pinapadali ko yong mga words na mhihirap Mas madali nilang maexpress yong sagot nila pag sila ay may mga group activity lalo na sa Grades 1-3.</i></p>

		<p><i>Nagpropvide ng materials upang mas Madali nila maintindihan upang mas lalo silang maging confident sa paggamit ng mother tongue.pu</i></p> <p><i>Mas Madaling matutunan ng bata</i></p> <p><i>Teachers can search and prepare the learner's strategies and methods in learning for the proper execution of lessons so that learners will understand it easily.</i></p>
	<i>Teacher Preparedness</i>	<p><i>Kapag MTB malaking tulong sa mga guro dahil nga mas nauunawaan din at mas naiipaliwanag ng guro ang mga lesson.</i></p> <p><i>Through different strategies and a more Interactive approach</i></p> <p><i>Prepared naman po dapat talaga ang mga guro.</i></p> <p><i>Siyempre dapat lagi tayong prepared laging gagawa ng paraan para maituro yong lesson</i></p> <p><i>Challenges face in preparedness help teachers to become more flexible in implementing strategies in order for the learners to understand more easily</i></p> <p><i>Yong mass training po mam pioneer kasi ang grade one noon pero sa tagal naman po nasanay.</i></p>
	<i>Parental Involvement</i>	<p><i>Minsan may mga parents na use sa ingles terms kay. medyo nahihiorapan sila pero ipinaliliwanag na lng po naming para mas maunawaan nila ito kapag may mga meetings</i></p> <p><i>Through parent academy naipapaliwanag sa mga magulang yong kanilang mga problema at natruturuan sila ng tama about MTB-MLE.</i></p> <p><i>Involving parents like sa mga meetings trainings para maintindihan nila ang gamit ng mother tounge instruction sa Mathematics.</i></p>

		<p><i>Pagbibigay ng assignment para mas magkaroon sila ng time na magkasama and maging bonding na din nila.</i></p> <p><i>Parents should be aware so that they should participate in the learning of their learners to help them and learned develop their skills</i></p> <p><i>Pagbibigay ng assignment para magkaroon ng update at learning ang bata at the same time magkakaroon sila ng time sa isat isa.</i></p>
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Table 8 presents the coping mechanism of teachers in addressing challenges encountered by the Teachers in Teaching Mathematics using Mother Tongue – Based Multilingual Education in Tagalog. Curriculum alignment highlights the strategies employed by teachers to address challenges in implementing Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) in Mathematics instruction. Teachers emphasize the relevance of using the mother tongue in facilitating learners understanding and communication, particularly in group activities where learners can express their answers more confidently. MTB-MLE has also improved Learners confidence and learning outcomes, making it easier for them to grasp mathematical concepts. Teachers play a crucial role in searching for and preparing appropriate strategies and methods to ensure the effective execution of lessons and enhance Learners comprehension.

Encouraging the use of the mother tongue and implementing interactive and Learners-centered teaching strategies are key to addressing challenges in curriculum alignment. Professional development programs should equip teachers with a diverse repertoire of instructional strategies that cater to the linguistic and learning needs of learners. Additionally, schools can foster a collaborative learning environment where teachers share best practices and support each other in implementing MTB-MLE effectively. By promoting teacher innovation and collaboration, educators can enhance curriculum alignment and improve Learners engagement and learning outcomes in Mathematics education.

Teacher preparedness highlights the importance of ongoing training and support for educators in implementing MTB-MLE in Mathematics instruction. Teachers recognize the benefits of MTB-MLE in enhancing their understanding and explanation of lessons, particularly through the use of different strategies and interactive approaches. However, challenges exist, including the need for teachers to continuously adapt and find ways to effectively teach lessons. Mass training initiatives have been instrumental in introducing MTB-MLE, but ongoing support is essential for teachers to become more flexible and confident in implementing strategies.

Strengthening teacher preparedness requires sustained investment in professional development programs that provide ongoing training and support tailored to the needs of educators. Mentorship programs and peer collaboration can facilitate

knowledge sharing and skill development among teachers, promoting a culture of continuous learning and improvement. Educational authorities should prioritize the provision of resources and support to ensure that teachers have the necessary tools and skills to effectively implement MTB-MLE in Mathematics instruction. By investing in teacher preparedness, educational stakeholders can enhance the quality of Mathematics education and promote positive learning outcomes for all learners.

Parental involvement underscores the importance of engaging parents in supporting their children's learning in MTB-MLE Mathematics education. Teachers recognize the challenges faced by parents in understanding and supporting MTB-MLE, particularly when English terms are used. However, efforts such as parent academies and regular communication help bridge the gap and facilitate parental understanding and involvement. Assignments and activities also provide opportunities for parents to spend time with their children and support their learning at home. Promoting parental involvement requires collaborative efforts between schools and families to provide resources, information, and support for parents in understanding and supporting MTB-MLE Mathematics education. Schools can offer parent workshops, resources, and regular communication channels to facilitate parental engagement and understanding. Additionally, educators can provide assignments and activities that encourage parent-child interaction and support learning at home. By fostering partnerships between schools and families, educators can enhance parental involvement and promote positive learning outcomes for learners in MTB-MLE Mathematics education.

Table 9
The Coping Mechanism of Teachers in Addressing Challenges Encountered by the Teachers in Teaching Mathematics Using Mother Tongue – Based Multilingual Instruction in Bicol

Theme	Sub-theme	Experiences
<i>Coping Mechanisms for Addressing Challenges</i>	<i>Curriculum Alignment</i>	<p><i>Dito sa min Yung mother tongue instruction mas nahihirapan sila kaya English na ginagamit naming kase mas naiintidihan</i></p> <p><i>Dapat ang Curriculum guide ng Mathematics ay nakaalign diin sa mother tongue Pag ang mga learners ko ay bicol binibicol ko rin siyempre para mas maunawaan. Dito sa grade 3 sinisimulan ko na English mas nauunawaan nila para mas hand ana sila sa grade 4</i></p> <p><i>Don sa mga terminologies na dapat malaman nila lalo na pagdating sa next level tinuturo ko na din.</i></p> <p><i>Ang mother tongue naman ay align kase nga mas naiintidihan nila pero pagdating sa grade 4 English na.</i></p>

<p><i>Teacher Preparedness</i></p>		<p><i>Syempre mahirap, so bilang paghahanda bukod sa binibigay ng mga trainees, kung hindi effective sa kanila kailangan mong gumawa ng paraan para maiangkop o malaman kung ano ang effective sa mga bata.</i></p> <p><i>Pag prepare ang teacher, Kinakaya lagi naman at school heads and master teacher kasi nga sila madalas nadalo sa mga trainings. Pero dapat laging ready tayo, pag may bagong curriculum kailangan natin i-adapt para lahat ng nasa curriculum ay maituro natin sa mga bata.</i></p> <p><i>Prepare ka lng lagi gumagawa ako ng mga instructional materials na makatutulong at mas effective sa kanila para mas maitindihan nila ang lesson.</i></p> <p><i>Dapat si teacher ay maraming visual aids/instructional Materials para mas maintindihan ng bata.</i></p>
<p><i>Parental Involvement</i></p>		<p><i>So kung ang parents sana ay malalim ang involvement sa bata mas magiging motivated o gaganahan mag-aral ang mga bata. Sinasabi naming ang mga problema sa mga bata para alam ng mga magulang. Ganun ang nagiging hirap ng isang teacher kapag involve na ang magulang</i></p> <p><i>Kailangan talaga natin ng tulong ng parental involvement, hindi lang yung slow learners ang kailangan turuan sa bahay, kailangan ay lahat sila. Meron tayong meeting kung saan tinatalakay natin yung problems and kung paano sila makakatulong sa bata, kaya humihingi ng tulong sa magulang na turuan sa pagdidisplina ng mga bata. Mayron tayong gc kung saan ibinabahagi natin ang mga updates tungkol sa bata at sa nangyayari sa eskwelahan.</i></p>

		<p><i>Kapag may meetings sinasabi sa mga parents ang problema sa mga bata lalo na sa Mathematics.</i></p> <p><i>Patawag ng meeting sa parent's para mas malaman nila ang mga problems and issue ng bata lalo na pagdating sa kanilang learning sa Mathematics.</i></p>
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Table 9 presents the coping mechanism of teachers in addressing challenges encountered by the teachers in teaching Mathematics using Mother Tongue –Multilingual Education in Bicol

The coping mechanisms for curriculum alignment in Bicol emphasize the importance of ensuring that instructional materials and teaching methods are aligned with the curriculum to enhance learners' understanding and skills. Teachers highlight the effectiveness of using the mother tongue in instruction, as it facilitates better comprehension and communication among learners. However, challenges arise when learners transition to higher grades where English becomes the medium of instruction. Despite this, teachers adapt their teaching strategies to ensure that learners grasp the necessary terminologies and concepts, thus maintaining alignment with the curriculum.

It implies that educators need ongoing support and resources to ensure that instructional materials and methods align with curriculum objectives. Professional development programs should focus on equipping teachers with effective strategies for teaching in multilingual environments and transitioning learners between language mediums. Additionally, collaboration between educators and curriculum developers is essential to ensure that instructional materials are culturally and linguistically relevant to learners. By prioritizing alignment with the curriculum, educators can enhance the effectiveness of instruction and promote positive learning outcomes for learners in Bicol.

The coping mechanisms for teacher preparedness highlight the importance of continuous professional development and adaptability in addressing challenges in implementing Mother Tongue Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) in Mathematics instruction. Teachers emphasize the need for flexibility and resourcefulness in adapting to new curricula and finding effective teaching methods for learners. They also stress the importance of visual aids and instructional materials in enhancing Learners understanding and engagement in the classroom. Enhancing teacher preparedness requires ongoing support and training that addresses the specific needs of educators in Bicol. Professional development programs should provide opportunities for teachers to learn and share effective instructional strategies, adapt to new curricular requirements, and utilize visual aids and instructional materials effectively. Additionally, mentorship programs and peer collaboration can facilitate knowledge sharing and skill development among teachers,

fostering a culture of continuous learning and improvement. By investing in teacher preparedness, educational stakeholders can enhance the quality of Mathematics education and promote positive learning outcomes for all learners.

The coping mechanisms for parental involvement underscore the importance of engaging parents in supporting their children's learning in Mathematics education. Teachers recognize the positive impact of parental involvement on Learners' motivation and academic success and actively seek to involve parents in their children's education through communication, meetings, and assignments. By fostering collaboration between educators and parents, teachers aim to address Learners' needs more effectively and promote a supportive learning environment both at school and at home.

Promoting parental involvement requires collaborative efforts between schools and families to provide resources, information, and support for parents in Bicol. Schools can offer workshops, communication channels, and regular meetings to facilitate parental engagement and understanding of their children's educational needs. Additionally, educators can provide assignments and activities that encourage parent-child interaction and support learning at home. By fostering partnerships between schools and families, educators can enhance parental involvement and promote positive learning outcomes for learners in Mathematics education.

According to Tortola (2021), most of the teachers became innovative in finding solutions to address the needs and problems of the learners. Teachers spent time in surfing the internet to look for additional resources since the Mathematics book has very limited resources. They downloaded instructional materials needed like worksheets and enhancement activities to enrich the learning of the learners. Some teachers claimed that when they encountered difficulties in deep terms or highly localized in Sinugbuanong Binisaya, they would ask the senior teacher or the co-teacher who was familiar with the terms. One way to make lessons easier to understand is the use of context clue. During classroom observation, the teacher simplified an unfamiliar term to simple Binisaya term. In situations like this, there is a need for a fluent teacher in the medium of instruction or in the mother tongue of her/his learners.

Part IV. Program to Enhance the Sustainability and Effectiveness of Using Mother Tongue in Teaching Mathematics

The program aimed at enhancing the sustainability and effectiveness of using the mother tongue in teaching Mathematics encompasses various critical aspects. Firstly, it is imperative for governments to officially endorse and support the integration of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) in Mathematics instruction, allocating resources and developing programs. Curriculum developers should ensure alignment between Mathematics curricula and MTB-MLE principles, incorporating culturally relevant content and indigenous knowledge. Furthermore, comprehensive teacher training and professional development programs are essential to equip educators with the necessary skills and strategies for effective implementation. The production of high-quality instructional materials in local languages is also vital to support teachers and learners in

the learning process. Additionally, fostering parent and community involvement is crucial for garnering support and creating a conducive learning environment. Regular monitoring and evaluation mechanisms should be established to assess program implementation and inform improvements. Finally, ongoing research and knowledge-sharing initiatives are necessary to document best practices and inform policy and practice. Through these concerted efforts, stakeholders can contribute to the sustainability and effectiveness of using the mother tongue in teaching Mathematics, ultimately promoting inclusive and culturally responsive education for all learners. The complete proposed program is in Appendix

DISCUSSION

Table 2 presents the positive experiences of teachers utilizing Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) in teaching Mathematics in primary education, particularly in Tagalog, three main themes emerge from the data: Learners Engagement, Conceptual Clarity, and Teaching Effectiveness, each highlighting specific advantages observed by the teachers.

In terms of pupil's Engagement, teachers report that learners understand lessons better and can answer questions more readily when taught in their mother tongue. This improved comprehension leads to more active participation and immediate responses to teacher inquiries. Furthermore, using Tagalog reduces learners' fear or shame, encouraging them to participate more willingly in classroom activities. The cultural relevance of commands and instructions in Tagalog resonates more deeply with learners, fostering a sense of connection and comfort in the learning environment.

When it comes to Conceptual Clarity, the use of the mother tongue simplifies problem-solving for learners. Mathematical concepts and problems explained in Tagalog are easier for learners to grasp and analyze. Teachers also find that instructions given in the mother tongue are clearer, helping learners to understand and complete their lessons and exams more effectively. This clarity leads to improved cooperation among learners' as they can better comprehend and follow the tasks assigned to them.

Regarding Teaching Effectiveness, teachers observe that learners' mean percentage scores have improved, indicating better academic performance. The use of Tagalog encourages all learners to participate in activities and solve problems correctly, demonstrating the effectiveness of this teaching approach. Additionally, teachers find it easier to prepare materials and conceptualize teaching strategies when using Tagalog, which enhances their overall teaching effectiveness. Despite some challenges in translating technical mathematical terms, the overall benefits of using the mother tongue outweigh these difficulties, resulting in more effective teaching.

It implies that the positive experiences of teachers in using Tagalog as MTB-MLE in teaching Mathematics underscore its potential to enhance learning outcomes and

promote learners' engagement. By addressing challenges and leveraging the benefits of MTB-MLE, educators can create a more effective and inclusive learning environment that caters to the diverse linguistic needs of learners in primary education.

Table 3 presents the negative experiences of teachers in teaching Mathematics in primary using Tagalog as mother tongue based multilingual education.

Teachers face significant challenges in teaching Mathematics using Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Education (MTB), particularly due to language barriers. learners, especially those from different linguistic backgrounds, struggle to grasp mathematical concepts presented in Tagalog, even though they are more accustomed to their mother tongue. This leads to difficulties in communication and comprehension, hindering effective teaching and learning. To address language barriers, educators need to adopt diverse instructional strategies that cater to the linguistic diversity of learners. This may include providing bilingual or multilingual resources, offering language support programs, and fostering a culturally responsive learning environment. Additionally, teacher training programs should focus on equipping educators with the necessary skills and tools to effectively teach Mathematics in multilingual settings, thereby improving learner engagement.

The reception of Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Education (MTB) in Mathematics varies among learners, influenced by factors such as language background and instructional support. Some learners may struggle to understand mathematical concepts presented in Tagalog, leading to confusion and frustration. However, with adequate support and encouragement, learners demonstrate resilience and willingness to learn, highlighting the importance of fostering a supportive learning environment. Educators must prioritize creating inclusive learning environments where learners feel supported and valued, regardless of their language background. This involves providing individualized support to learners who may struggle with language comprehension, implementing collaborative learning activities that promote peer interaction and support, and celebrating linguistic and cultural diversity in the classroom. By addressing learners' diverse needs and fostering a positive learning environment, educators can enhance learners reception of MTB in Mathematics and promote equitable access to education for all learners.

Resource limitations pose significant challenges to the implementation of Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Education (MTB) in Mathematics, impacting the quality of instruction and learning outcomes. Teachers often lack sufficient instructional materials and training opportunities, forcing them to create local materials and adapt teaching strategies to address resource gaps. This not only consumes valuable time and effort but also affects the effectiveness of teaching and learning. Addressing resource limitations requires a multi-faceted approach that involves both policy-level interventions and localized strategies. Governments and educational authorities should prioritize investment in education infrastructure, including the provision of adequate instructional materials, training opportunities for teachers, and support for curriculum development in local languages. Additionally, educators can leverage existing resources more efficiently

through collaborative networks, sharing best practices, and tapping into community resources. By addressing resource limitations comprehensively, educators can enhance the implementation of MTB in Mathematics and improve Learners learning outcomes.

Furthermore, a balance between mastery of the facts of higher order thinking skills translated into the native dialect must be forged by the teachers in their choice of a teaching strategy, selecting appropriate teaching strategy and suited for the level of the learner, and mastery of prerequisite knowledge or concept as translated in the native dialect (Ball, 2010) as cited by Tortola (2021)

Table 4 presents the positive experiences of teachers employing Bicol as their Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) in teaching Mathematics in the Bicol region focusing on learners engagement, conceptual clarity, and teaching effectiveness.

Teachers observe that using MTB-MLE significantly enhances engagement, especially when lessons are translated into Tagalog or Bicol. Most learners are Bicolano, and they respond better to instruction in their native language, leading to more productive lessons. This approach helps learners comprehend better and participate more actively. Teachers note that learners understand problem situations better in their mother tongue compared to English, which was previously used. Although there are challenges with terminology differences, especially when transitioning between Tagalog and Bicol, the overall engagement and confidence of learners have increased. This boost in confidence is attributed to their improved understanding of the lessons, facilitated by the use of their mother tongue.

Using the mother tongue in teaching mathematical concepts enhances learners' understanding and clarity. Teachers find that instructions are clearer, and learners' grasp mathematical terms and concepts more effectively. When learners speak and learn in their mother tongue, they can express themselves better and engage more meaningfully in problem-solving activities. This clarity extends to specific instructions, making it easier for learners to follow along and respond accurately. Teachers report that learners immediately understand and apply instructions when taught in their mother tongue, reducing the need for repeated explanations. This immediate comprehension leads to smoother classroom interactions and better academic performance in Mathematics.

Teachers experience improved teaching effectiveness with the use of Bicol as MTB-MLE. Daily instruction in the mother tongue helps learners understand lessons more easily, leading to better academic outcomes. Although there is a noted challenge when learners transition to higher grades where English is the primary medium of instruction, the foundational understanding built through MTB-MLE remains beneficial. Teachers find that using materials in the mother tongue makes lessons more effective and helps learners quickly grasp and retain mathematical concepts. This effectiveness is particularly evident in exams, where learners demonstrate quicker understanding and accurate responses. Teachers emphasize that being effective in their instruction is crucial for expanding learners learning and understanding. Overall, the use of the mother tongue

proves to be an effective strategy in enhancing the teaching and learning process in primary Mathematics education.

The positive experiences with MTB-MLE in Bicol highlight the need for educational policies that support multilingual education, especially in regions with diverse linguistic backgrounds. Developing comprehensive bilingual or multilingual resources can help standardize terminology and improve understanding. Providing continuous professional development and training for teachers in MTB-MLE methodologies is essential to equip them with effective strategies for engaging learners and enhancing conceptual clarity. Allocating adequate resources, including textbooks and teaching aids in both Tagalog and regional dialects, is crucial to support MTB-MLE. Additionally, involving parents and the community in the educational process can reinforce classroom learning and provide additional support for learners. Regular assessment and feedback mechanisms can help identify best practices and areas for improvement, ensuring the sustained success of MTB-MLE programs. By addressing these implications, the effectiveness of teaching Mathematics in primary education using MTB-MLE in Bicol can be further enhanced, leading to better academic outcomes and Learners' engagement.

According to Englis, & Boholano (2021), the use of mother-tongue in teaching Mathematics is effective in acquiring Mathematical knowledge. The teachers are well-prepared in terms of content and instructional material preparation. Moreover, the contextualized and innovative model in teaching Mathematics using mother-tongue helps in acquiring basic skills in Mathematics hence, in order to help the Mathematics teachers in making use of this model, this finding would be a great help to the primary teachers in Mathematics as well as the institution the value of contextualization and innovation as core functions in teaching strategies where the school administrators will continually support the teachers development plan and provide the tools and equipment needed on teaching.

Table 5 presents the negative experiences of teachers in teaching Mathematics in primary using Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Instruction in Bicol

The experience of language barriers in Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) in Bicol underscores the complexity of linguistic diversity in educational settings. Teachers face challenges in translating mathematical concepts from Tagalog to Bicol, as some terms may not have direct equivalents. Additionally, Learners may struggle with deeper concepts like problem-solving due to language limitations, impacting their comprehension and learning experiences. Despite efforts to bridge the language gap, such as using English for clarification, challenges persist for both learners' and teachers, particularly when learners come from different linguistic backgrounds.

The reception of MTB-MLE in Mathematics among learners in Bicol varies based on individual abilities, linguistic backgrounds, and previous experiences with Mathematics instruction. While MTB-MLE may be effective for some learners, others may struggle, particularly if they come from different linguistic backgrounds or have varying levels of mathematical proficiency. Teachers play a crucial role in supporting Learners

understanding by providing language support and adapting instructional strategies to meet diverse learning needs. However, challenges persist, particularly when learners' transition from day care to Grade I, where they may encounter difficulties due to language preferences and writing conventions.

Resource limitations pose significant challenges to the effective implementation of MTB-MLE in Mathematics instruction in Bicol. Teachers lack adequate instructional materials, including books and digital resources, impacting their ability to deliver high-quality instruction. Despite efforts to supplement resources with internet access and teacher guides, limitations persist, leading to reliance on shared materials and improvised teaching methods. Additionally, challenges arise in accessing indigenous materials and ensuring equitable distribution of resources across schools.

It implies that language barriers require a multi-pronged approach that acknowledges the diverse linguistic landscape of the classroom. Educators should collaborate with local communities to develop comprehensive language resources that cater to the specific needs of learners, including translations of mathematical terms and concepts. Professional development programs should focus on equipping teachers with strategies for effectively teaching in multilingual environments, such as code-switching and incorporating culturally relevant examples. Moreover, educational policies should prioritize the inclusion of diverse languages in curriculum development and instructional materials, ensuring equitable access to education for all learners. Enhancing Learners reception of MTB-MLE in Mathematics requires a holistic approach that addresses individual learning needs and linguistic diversity. Educators should implement differentiated instruction strategies that accommodate diverse learning styles and abilities, providing additional support for learners' who may struggle with mathematical concepts. Furthermore, collaboration between educators, parents, and communities is essential to create a supportive learning environment that values linguistic diversity and promotes academic success for all earners. By fostering a culture of inclusivity and support, educators can empower learners to overcome challenges and thrive in Mathematics education. Moreover, resource limitations required systemic changes at both policy and practice levels. Educational authorities should prioritize investment in educational infrastructure, including the provision of sufficient instructional materials and digital resources, to support effective teaching and learning. Furthermore, professional development programs should equip teachers with the skills and knowledge to utilize available resources effectively and adapt teaching strategies to meet diverse learning needs. Collaborative efforts between government agencies, educational institutions, and community stakeholders are essential to ensure equitable access to resources and promote educational equity in Bicol and beyond.

Table 6 presents the challenges towards the used of MTB-MLE as a medium of instruction in Mathematics were encountered by the teachers in Tagalog. Curriculum alignment highlights the challenges and successes of aligning the Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) approach with the Mathematics curriculum. Teachers express varying degrees of ease or difficulty in implementing MTB-MLE in Mathematics instruction, depending on their familiarity with the curriculum and the training they have

received. While some teachers find it relatively easy to align the MTB-MLE approach with the curriculum, others struggle due to complex mathematical terminologies and lack of training. Despite these challenges, teachers acknowledge the benefits of using MTB-MLE, particularly in helping both teachers and learners understand lesson objectives and execute activities effectively. Enhancing curriculum alignment requires targeted support for teachers, including comprehensive training on curriculum objectives and strategies for integrating MTB-MLE in Mathematics instruction. Professional development programs should focus on building teachers' capacity to effectively translate complex mathematical concepts into mother tongue languages and adapt instructional materials to suit diverse learning needs. Additionally, educational authorities should provide ongoing guidance and resources to support teachers in aligning MTB-MLE with the Mathematics curriculum, ensuring consistency and effectiveness in teaching practices.

Teacher preparedness underscores the challenges faced by teachers in implementing MTB-MLE in Mathematics due to inadequate training and preparation.

Promoting parental involvement in MTB-MLE requires targeted outreach and support initiatives that empower parents to actively engage in their children's education. Schools and educational authorities should provide resources and information in languages accessible to parents, including translations of curriculum materials and guidance on how to support MTB-MLE at home. Additionally, parent-teacher collaboration platforms and workshops can facilitate communication and collaboration between educators and parents, fostering a supportive learning environment for learners. By promoting parental involvement, educators can enhance the effectiveness of MTB-MLE in Mathematics education and promote positive learning outcomes for all learners.

Melencion (2017) as cited by Tortola (2021), stated that some teachers are asked to teach some other language or vernacular, multilingual dialects that are unfamiliar to them. These points to the difficulty of using the MTBMLE since there are different variations of the mother tongue even in one locality.

Table 7 presents the challenges towards the used of MTB-MLE as a medium of instruction in Mathematics were encountered by the teachers in Bicol.

Curriculum alignment highlights both the challenges and successes in aligning the Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) approach with the Mathematics curriculum in Bicol. Teachers express difficulties in translating certain mathematical terms into the mother tongue, necessitating the use of English for explanation. However, they also emphasize the importance of alignment between the curriculum and teaching practices, acknowledging the efforts made to ensure coherence and effectiveness in instruction. Teachers demonstrate adaptability in addressing challenges, such as providing translations for difficult terms, and recognize the value of implementing MTB-MLE despite its complexities.

Ensuring effective curriculum alignment requires ongoing collaboration and communication between educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers.

Educational authorities should provide comprehensive guidance and resources to support teachers in aligning MTB-MLE with the Mathematics curriculum, including translations of difficult terms and clear guidelines for implementation. Additionally, professional development programs should equip teachers with the skills and knowledge needed to effectively integrate MTB-MLE into Mathematics instruction, fostering a deeper understanding of curriculum objectives and instructional strategies. By promoting alignment between the curriculum and teaching practices, educators can enhance the effectiveness of MTB-MLE in Mathematics education and improve learning outcomes for learners.

Teacher preparedness reflects the challenges and efforts involved in ensuring that educators are adequately trained and equipped to implement MTB-MLE in Mathematics instruction. Teachers express varying levels of preparedness, with some feeling confident in their training and others acknowledging the ongoing nature of professional development. Despite challenges, such as the transition to online training during the pandemic, teachers demonstrate a commitment to continuous improvement and recognize the importance of training in enhancing their effectiveness as educators.

Enhancing teacher preparedness requires sustained investment in professional development opportunities that address the specific needs of educators in implementing MTB-MLE in Mathematics instruction. Educational authorities should provide ongoing training and support that is aligned with curriculum objectives and instructional priorities. Additionally, mentorship programs and peer collaboration can facilitate knowledge sharing and skill development among educators, fostering a culture of continuous learning and improvement. By prioritizing teacher preparedness, educational stakeholders can enhance the quality of Mathematics education and promote positive learning outcomes for all learners.

Parental involvement underscores the challenges and importance of parental support in facilitating Learners learning in MTB-MLE Mathematics education. Teachers note the impact of parental attitudes and engagement on learners success, highlighting the influence of factors such as parental availability, educational background, and willingness to support their children's learning. Challenges arise when parents lack the time, resources, or understanding to effectively support their children's education, leading to disparities in Learners outcomes.

Promoting parental involvement requires targeted efforts to engage and support parents in their children's education, particularly in understanding and supporting MTB-MLE Mathematics instruction. Schools can provide resources and guidance to parents on how to support their children's learning at home, including translations of curriculum materials and strategies for reinforcing mathematical concepts. Additionally, schools can foster a culture of collaboration between educators and parents, encouraging open communication and mutual support. By addressing barriers to parental involvement and promoting a supportive home learning environment, educators can enhance learners success in MTB-MLE Mathematics education.

Table 8 presents the coping mechanism of teachers in addressing challenges encountered by the Teachers in Teaching Mathematics using Mother Tongue – Based Multilingual Education in Tagalog. Curriculum alignment highlights the strategies employed by teachers to address challenges in implementing Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) in Mathematics instruction. Teachers emphasize the relevance of using the mother tongue in facilitating learners understanding and communication, particularly in group activities where learners can express their answers more confidently. MTB-MLE has also improved Learners confidence and learning outcomes, making it easier for them to grasp mathematical concepts. Teachers play a crucial role in searching for and preparing appropriate strategies and methods to ensure the effective execution of lessons and enhance Learners comprehension.

Encouraging the use of the mother tongue and implementing interactive and Learners-centered teaching strategies are key to addressing challenges in curriculum alignment. Professional development programs should equip teachers with a diverse repertoire of instructional strategies that cater to the linguistic and learning needs of learners. Additionally, schools can foster a collaborative learning environment where teachers share best practices and support each other in implementing MTB-MLE effectively. By promoting teacher innovation and collaboration, educators can enhance curriculum alignment and improve Learners engagement and learning outcomes in Mathematics education.

Teacher preparedness highlights the importance of ongoing training and support for educators in implementing MTB-MLE in Mathematics instruction. Teachers recognize the benefits of MTB-MLE in enhancing their understanding and explanation of lessons, particularly through the use of different strategies and interactive approaches. However, challenges exist, including the need for teachers to continuously adapt and find ways to effectively teach lessons. Mass training initiatives have been instrumental in introducing MTB-MLE, but ongoing support is essential for teachers to become more flexible and confident in implementing strategies.

Strengthening teacher preparedness requires sustained investment in professional development programs that provide ongoing training and support tailored to the needs of educators. Mentorship programs and peer collaboration can facilitate knowledge sharing and skill development among teachers, promoting a culture of continuous learning and improvement. Educational authorities should prioritize the provision of resources and support to ensure that teachers have the necessary tools and skills to effectively implement MTB-MLE in Mathematics instruction. By investing in teacher preparedness, educational stakeholders can enhance the quality of Mathematics education and promote positive learning outcomes for all learners.

Parental involvement underscores the importance of engaging parents in supporting their children's learning in MTB-MLE Mathematics education. Teachers recognize the challenges faced by parents in understanding and supporting MTB-MLE, particularly when English terms are used. However, efforts such as parent academies and regular communication help bridge the gap and facilitate parental understanding and

involvement. Assignments and activities also provide opportunities for parents to spend time with their children and support their learning at home. Promoting parental involvement requires collaborative efforts between schools and families to provide resources, information, and support for parents in understanding and supporting MTB-MLE Mathematics education. Schools can offer parent workshops, resources, and regular communication channels to facilitate parental engagement and understanding. Additionally, educators can provide assignments and activities that encourage parent-child interaction and support learning at home. By fostering partnerships between schools and families, educators can enhance parental involvement and promote positive learning outcomes for learners in MTB-MLE Mathematics education.

Table 9 presents the coping mechanism of teachers in addressing challenges encountered by the teachers in teaching Mathematics using Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education in Bicol

The coping mechanisms for curriculum alignment in Bicol emphasize the importance of ensuring that instructional materials and teaching methods are aligned with the curriculum to enhance learner's understanding and skills. Teachers highlight the effectiveness of using the mother tongue in instruction, as it facilitates better comprehension and communication among learners. However, challenges arise when learners transition to higher grades where English becomes the medium of instruction. Despite this, teachers adapt their teaching strategies to ensure that learners grasp the necessary terminologies and concepts, thus maintaining alignment with the curriculum.

It implies that educators need ongoing support and resources to ensure that instructional materials and methods align with curriculum objectives. Professional development programs should focus on equipping teachers with effective strategies for teaching in multilingual environments and transitioning learners between language mediums. Additionally, collaboration between educators and curriculum developers is essential to ensure that instructional materials are culturally and linguistically relevant to learners. By prioritizing alignment with the curriculum, educators can enhance the effectiveness of instruction and promote positive learning outcomes for learners' in Bicol.

The coping mechanisms for teacher preparedness highlight the importance of continuous professional development and adaptability in addressing challenges in implementing Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) in Mathematics instruction. Teachers emphasize the need for flexibility and resourcefulness in adapting to new curricula and finding effective teaching methods for learners. They also stress the importance of visual aids and instructional materials in enhancing Learners understanding and engagement in the classroom. Enhancing teacher preparedness requires ongoing support and training that addresses the specific needs of educators in Bicol. Professional development programs should provide opportunities for teachers to learn and share effective instructional strategies, adapt to new curricular requirements, and utilize visual aids and instructional materials effectively. Additionally, mentorship programs and peer collaboration can facilitate knowledge sharing and skill development among teachers, fostering a culture of continuous learning and improvement. By investing in teacher

preparedness, educational stakeholders can enhance the quality of Mathematics education and promote positive learning outcomes for all learners.

The coping mechanisms for parental involvement underscore the importance of engaging parents in supporting their children's learning in Mathematics education. Teachers recognize the positive impact of parental involvement on Learners motivation and academic success and actively seek to involve parents in their children's education through communication, meetings, and assignments. By fostering collaboration between educators and parents, teachers aim to address Learners needs more effectively and promote a supportive learning environment both at school and at home.

Promoting parental involvement requires collaborative efforts between schools and families to provide resources, information, and support for parents in Bicol. Schools can offer workshops, communication channels, and regular meetings to facilitate parental engagement and understanding of their children's educational needs. Additionally, educators can provide assignments and activities that encourage parent-child interaction and support learning at home. By fostering partnerships between schools and families, educators can enhance parental involvement and promote positive learning outcomes for learners' in Mathematics education.

According to Tortola (2021), most of the teachers became innovative in finding solutions to address the needs and problems of the learners. Teachers spent time in surfing the internet to look for additional resources since the Mathematics book has very limited resources. They downloaded instructional materials needed like worksheets and enhancement activities to enrich the learning of the learners. Some teachers claimed that when they encountered difficulties in deep terms or highly localized in Sinugbuanong Binisaya, they would ask the senior teacher or the co-teacher who was familiar with the terms. One way to make lessons easier to understand is the use of context clue. During classroom observation, the teacher simplified an unfamiliar term to simple Binisaya term. In situations like this, there is a need for a fluent teacher in the medium of instruction or in the mother tongue

Summary

This study was conducted to explore the experiences of teachers in teaching Mathematics using Mother Tongue – Based Multilingual Education across South Luzon. The qualitative research is designed to gain in-depth insights into the experiences, challenges, and strategies of teachers in South Luzon. Qualitative research is well-suited for exploring complex phenomena and understanding the lived experiences of participants. This design allows for a nuanced exploration of the multifaceted aspects of MTB-MLE in Mathematics instruction. The study is to be conducted across selected elementary schools in Quezon and Bicol Regions. The researcher chose schools in Quezon, namely, Pedro Cabangon Elementary School Located at Brgy. Mascariña, Quezon, Quezon and Del Pilar Elementary School Located at Brgy. Del Pilar Quezon, Quezon. While across the Bicol Region, Dygico Elementary School Sta Elena Camarines Norte and San Pedro Elementary School San Pedro, Camarines Norte. The researcher

participants are composed of 6 teachers in Quezon District who are actively teaching MTB-MLE and teachers from Grades 1-3 in Dygico Elementary School and San Pedro Elementary School. The choice of South Luzon is based on its linguistic diversity and the significant implementation of MTB-MLE in the region.

The research population for this study encompasses educators based in South Luzon actively engaged in instructing Mathematics through the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) framework. This diverse group of teachers represents various linguistic backgrounds and spans different educational levels. To ensure a comprehensive and representative sample, a purposive sampling technique will be utilized. near the researcher's These chosen schools were specifically identified for their implementation of MTB-MLE in Tagalog, and Bicol languages, aligning with the study's focus on multilingual instructional contexts. The primary data collection instrument will be interviews and observations. An interview guide will be developed, consisting of open-ended questions designed to elicit teachers' experiences, challenges, strategies, and perceptions regarding MTB-MLE in Mathematics instruction. The interview guide will be pre-tested to ensure clarity and effectiveness.

Findings

The study yielded the following findings.

The study yielded the following findings.

1. The positive and negative experiences of teachers in teaching Mathematics in primary using Mother Tongue - Based Multilingual Instruction.
 - 1.1 The positive experiences of teachers in teaching Mathematics in primary using Mother Tongue Multilingual Education. Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) in Tagalog. Learners Engagement, Conceptual Clarity, and Teaching Effectiveness, each showcasing specific benefits observed by teachers. Teachers note that learners understand lessons better and can respond more readily when taught in their mother tongue, Tagalog. This improved comprehension leads to more active participation and quicker responses. Additionally, using Tagalog reduces learners' fear or shame, encouraging more willing participation in classroom activities. The cultural relevance of Tagalog commands and instructions resonates deeply, fostering a sense of connection and comfort in the learning environment. The use of the mother tongue simplifies problem-solving for learners. Mathematical concepts and problems explained in Tagalog are easier for learners to grasp and analyze. Teachers find that instructions given in the mother tongue are clearer, helping Learners understand and complete their lessons and exams more effectively. This clarity enhances learners' cooperation as they better comprehend and follow assigned tasks. Furthermore, teachers observe improved academic performance, as indicated by higher mean percentage scores. The use of Tagalog encourages all learners to participate in activities and solve problems correctly, demonstrating the effectiveness of this teaching

approach. Additionally, it is easier for teachers to prepare materials and conceptualize teaching strategies when using Tagalog, enhancing their overall teaching effectiveness. Despite some challenges in translating technical mathematical terms, the benefits of using the mother tongue outweigh these difficulties, resulting in more effective teaching. The positive experiences of teachers using MTB-MLE (Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education) in teaching Mathematics highlight its potential to enhance learning outcomes and promote Learner engagement. By addressing challenges and leveraging the benefits of MTB-MLE, educators can create a more effective and inclusive learning environment that caters to the diverse linguistic needs of primary education learners.

1.2 The positive experiences of teachers in teaching Mathematics in primary using Mother tongue-based Multilingual Education. Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) in Bicol. Teachers observe that using MTB-MLE (Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education) significantly enhances Learner's engagement, especially when lessons are translated into Tagalog or Bicol. Most learners, being Bicolano, respond better to instruction in their native language, leading to more productive lessons and active participation. Although there are terminology challenges, the overall Learners' engagement and confidence have increased due to better comprehension of lessons. Using the mother tongue in teaching mathematical concepts improves learners' understanding and clarity. Instructions are clearer, and learners grasp terms and concepts more effectively, leading to smoother classroom interactions and better academic performance.

Teachers also experience improved teaching effectiveness with MTB-MLE. Lessons in the mother tongue result in better academic outcomes, and while transitioning to English in higher grades is challenging, the foundational understanding built through MTB-MLE remains beneficial. The use of mother tongue materials makes lessons more effective, helping learners quickly grasp and retain concepts.

The positive experiences with MTB-MLE in Bicol highlight the need for policies supporting multilingual education. Developing bilingual resources, providing teacher training, and involving the community can enhance the effectiveness of MTB-MLE, leading to better academic outcomes and Learner engagement.

2. The negative experiences of teachers in teaching Mathematics in primary using Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Instruction. ,

2.1 The negative experiences of teachers in teaching Mathematics in primary using Mother Tongue Multilingual Education. Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Instruction (MTB-MLE) in Tagalog. Teachers face significant challenges in teaching Mathematics using Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-

MLE) due to language barriers. learners from diverse linguistic backgrounds struggle with mathematical concepts in Tagalog, leading to difficulties in communication and comprehension. To address these issues, educators need to adopt diverse instructional strategies, provide bilingual resources, offer language support programs, and foster culturally responsive learning environments. Teacher training should equip educators with skills to teach in multilingual settings, enhancing Learner's engagement.

The reception of MTB-MLE in Mathematics varies among learners, with some struggling to understand concepts in Tagalog. However, with adequate support, learners show resilience and willingness to learn. Educators must create inclusive learning environments, provide individualized support, implement collaborative learning activities, and celebrate linguistic diversity. This improves Learners' reception of MTB-MLE and promotes equitable education.

Resource limitations also pose significant challenges, impacting instruction quality. Teachers often lack sufficient materials and training, leading to resource gaps. Addressing these limitations requires policy-level interventions and localized strategies. Governments should invest in educational infrastructure, provide instructional materials and training, and support curriculum development. Educators can leverage resources through collaborative networks and community involvement, enhancing MTB-MLE implementation and improving Learner's outcomes.

2.2 The negative experiences of teachers in teaching Mathematics in primary using Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Instruction. Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) in Bicol. Language barriers in MTB-MLE in Bicol complicate education, as translating mathematical concepts from Tagalog to Bicol is challenging. This affects learners' comprehension and problem-solving skills, despite using English for clarification. The reception of MTB-MLE in Mathematics varies among learners, influenced by their linguistic backgrounds and prior math experiences. Teachers play a crucial role in supporting learners, but challenges persist, especially during transitions from daycare to Grade I. Resource limitations, such as insufficient instructional materials, further hinder effective MTB-MLE implementation, despite efforts to supplement with internet access and shared materials.

3. The challenges towards the use of MTB-MLE as a medium of instruction in

Mathematics encountered by the teachers.

3.1 The teachers in Tagalog encountered challenges in using MTB-MLE as a medium of instruction in Mathematics. the challenges encountered by Tagalog-speaking teachers in using MTB-MLE as a medium of instruction in Mathematics are Curriculum alignment poses difficulties for teachers in effectively integrating MTB-MLE

with the Mathematics curriculum, with varying degrees of ease depending on their familiarity and training. Despite challenges, teachers recognize the benefits of MTB-MLE in clarifying lesson objectives and activities. To enhance alignment, targeted support through comprehensive training and ongoing guidance is necessary. Teacher preparedness is hindered by inadequate training, emphasizing the need for professional development programs tailored to address curriculum alignment, language proficiency, and instructional strategies. Improving teacher preparedness is essential for equitable and effective MTB-MLE implementation. Parental involvement varies, with some parents actively supporting their children's learning while others struggle to engage with the curriculum. Promoting parental involvement requires outreach efforts, accessible resources, and collaboration platforms to foster a supportive learning environment and enhance the effectiveness of MTB-MLE in Mathematics education.

3.2. The teachers in Bicol encountered challenges with the use of MTB-MLE as a medium of instruction in Mathematics. The challenges faced by Bicol-speaking teachers in implementing MTB-MLE as a medium of instruction in Mathematics are Curriculum alignment poses difficulties, particularly in translating mathematical terms into the mother tongue, but teachers emphasize its importance for effective instruction. They demonstrate adaptability in addressing challenges and recognize the value of MTB-MLE despite complexities. Ongoing collaboration and guidance are essential for effective alignment, requiring support from educational authorities and comprehensive professional development for teachers. Teacher preparedness varies, with efforts needed to ensure continuous improvement through tailored training and mentorship programs. Parental involvement is crucial for Learner's success in MTB-MLE Mathematics education, requiring targeted efforts to engage and support parents in understanding and supporting their children's learning at home. By addressing these challenges, educators can enhance the effectiveness of MTB-MLE in Mathematics education and improve learning outcomes for learners.

4. The coping mechanism of teachers in addressing challenges encountered by the Teachers in Teaching Mathematics using Mother Tongue – Based Multilingual Instruction

4.1 The coping mechanism of teachers in addressing challenges encountered by the Teachers in Teaching Mathematics using Mother Tongue- Multilingual Instruction in Tagalog employed by Tagalog-speaking teachers to address challenges in teaching Mathematics using Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE). Curriculum alignment strategies focus on utilizing the mother tongue to enhance Learners understanding and confidence, particularly in interactive group activities. Teachers emphasize the importance of professional development programs to equip them with diverse instructional strategies tailored to learners' linguistic and learning needs. Encouraging teacher innovation and collaboration fosters effective curriculum alignment and improves Learner engagement. Teacher preparedness involves ongoing training and support to enhance educators' flexibility and confidence in implementing MTB-MLE strategies. Sustained investment in professional

development, mentorship programs, and peer collaboration is crucial to ensure teachers have the necessary skills for effective instruction. Parental involvement initiatives such as parent academies and regular communication channels help bridge the gap in understanding and support for MTB-MLE Mathematics education. Collaborative efforts between schools and families, including workshops and activities, promote parental engagement and enhance Learners learning outcomes.

4.2. The coping mechanism of teachers in addressing challenges encountered by the Teachers in Teaching Mathematics using Mother Tongue –Multilingual Instruction in Bicol. The coping mechanisms employed by Bicol-speaking teachers to address challenges in teaching Mathematics using Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE). Curriculum alignment strategies focus on ensuring instructional materials and methods align with the curriculum to enhance Learners understanding. Teachers highlight the effectiveness of using the mother tongue in instruction but adapt strategies as learners transition to English-medium instruction in higher grades. Ongoing support and resources are essential for teachers to maintain alignment with curriculum objectives, with professional development programs focusing on effective teaching strategies and collaboration with curriculum developers. Teacher preparedness emphasizes continuous professional development and adaptability in implementing MTB-MLE, with a focus on effective instructional strategies and the use of visual aids. Ongoing support and training tailored to the specific needs of educators in Bicol are crucial for enhancing teacher preparedness. Parental involvement initiatives aim to engage parents in supporting their children's learning in Mathematics education through communication, meetings, and assignments. Collaborative efforts between schools and families, including workshops and regular meetings, promote parental engagement and support learning at home, ultimately enhancing Learner's outcomes in Mathematics education.

5. The program proposal can be made to enhance the sustainability and effectiveness of using Mother Tongue in Teaching Mathematics. To enhance the sustainability and effectiveness of using Mother Tongue in teaching Mathematics, policymakers should officially endorse MTB-MLE integration, ensure curriculum alignment, provide comprehensive teacher training, produce high-quality instructional materials, foster parent and community involvement, establish monitoring mechanisms, and promote ongoing research and knowledge sharing. These efforts aim to create inclusive and culturally responsive education, benefiting all learners.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The findings revealed that Mother tongue-based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) significantly improves instructional practices and Learners' learning outcomes in primary Mathematics education. By using learners' native language, MTB-MLE enhances engagement, comprehension, and problem-

solving skills, fostering confidence and active class participation. Despite its benefits, MTB-MLE presents challenges for teachers, including language barriers and resource limitations. Translation difficulties and inadequate instructional materials hinder Learner's comprehension and engagement in Mathematics learning.

2. According to research findings, implementing MTB-MLE for Mathematics instruction faces challenges such as curriculum alignment and teacher preparedness. Comprehensive alignment between curriculum objectives and instructional materials is crucial, along with targeted professional development for teachers and fostering parental involvement.
3. The findings of this study, teachers employ coping mechanisms to address challenges in MTB-MLE implementation, including ensuring relevance and comprehensibility of the mother tongue in instruction. They utilize interactive approaches, prepare instructional strategies, and emphasize continuous professional development and parental involvement to support Learner's learning.
4. To enhance the sustainability and effectiveness of using Mother Tongue in teaching Mathematics, policymakers should endorse MTB-MLE integration, ensure curriculum alignment, provide comprehensive teacher training, foster parent and community involvement, establish monitoring mechanisms, and promote ongoing research and knowledge sharing. These efforts aim to create inclusive and culturally responsive education, benefiting all learners.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are hereby suggested:

1. Since the findings revealed that using Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Instruction in Mathematics faces challenges including language barriers, resource limitations, translation difficulties, and inadequate instructional materials that affect the Learners' comprehension and engagement in Mathematics learning, it is recommended to DepEd officials to establish teacher training programs focused on MTB-MLE implantation strategies and provide ongoing support and resource for Learners School Heads.
2. After seeing the result of the study that using Mother Tongue for Mathematics instruction faces challenges such as curriculum alignment and teacher preparedness and comprehensive alignment between curriculum objectives and instructional materials is crucial, School heads may target professional development for teachers to support them in implementing Mother Tongue Based-Multilingual Instruction by providing leadership, resources, and professional development opportunities.

3. In as much the findings revealed that teachers face challenges in Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Instruction, including ensuring relevance and comprehensibility of the mother tongue in instruction, hence they may utilize interactive approaches, prepare instructional strategies, and emphasize continuous professional development and parental involvement to support learners' learning. Include encouraging teachers, to embrace Mother Tongue-Based Instruction as a pedagogical approach and seek professional development opportunities to enhance skills in teaching Mathematics using the mother tongue.
4. According to the findings of the study the learners struggle due to complex mathematical terminologies and lack of vocabulary, teachers may provide instructional materials such as flashcards, and vocabulary words written on strips of paper for the learners to become more active and participate in Mathematics lessons conducted in the mother tongue and seek assistance from teachers when needed.
5. Since the study of Experiences of Teachers in Teaching Mathematics using Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Instruction is limited only across South Luzon, future Researchers may conduct research studies in a wider range to evaluate the long-term impact and effectiveness of using Mother Tongue-Based Instruction in teaching Mathematics.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

All participants, including educators, administrators, and other relevant stakeholders, provided informed consent before their involvement in the study, which was initially acquired by the researcher. The participants were informed about the purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits of the study. They were also given the freedom to withdraw from it at any time without incurring any penalties. Confidentiality and anonymity were also maintained to protect the privacy of the participants, ensuring that their responses and personal data were kept private and not disclosed without their express consent. In addition, the research was conducted with honesty, integrity, and transparency of fraud or manipulation.

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